

can be raised year round with this system.

Bamboo platforms were attached to two large airtight oil drums. The tops of the rafts were covered with damaged gunny sacks and a thin 7.5-cm layer of rice soil was spread over the surface.

We compared the performance of 10 short-duration rice varieties on 3- × 3-m floating rafts with 3 replications. Seedlings were transplanted 18 d after seeding in Jun 1985 (wet season).

Crop growth was satisfactory (see table). □

Growth characteristics, yield attributes, and yield of rice varieties grown on floating rafts. Vellayani, India, 1985 kharif.

Variety	Height (cm)	Tillers/hill	Productive tillers/hill	Percentage of panicles/hill	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grains/panicle	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
Cul. 170	62	28	26	93	14	36	4.0	6.9
Cul. 8	92	27	23	85	18	30	4.0	6.7
Karthika	102	25	22	88	20	30	2.0	5.0
Mo-5	90	28	22	78	19	32	2.7	6.8
Pavizham	95	21	16	76	18	25	2.1	6.1
Mo-4	100	11	9	82	19	22	1.7	6.9
Triveni	102	21	18	82	19	39	4.6	6.4
Bhadra	82	18	16	89	17	32	2.7	6.8
Kochuvithu	110	14	10	71	20	21	2.0	5.5
Cul. 93	105	23	20	87	20.5	43	4.7	8.7

Effect of land preparation on control of *Paspalum distichum*

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We tested tillage to control perennial grass weed *Paspalum distichum* L. in transplanted rice in Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines.

Total dry weed weight in unweeded plots was highest with 1 plowing + 3 harrowings by hand tractor; *Echinochloa glabrescens* Munro ex Hook. f. accounted for the bulk of the weed growth (see table).

The intensive soil turning by the hand tractor reduced growth of *P. distichum*, but not significantly. It could have brought seeds of *E. glabrescens* to the

surface or scarified them, resulting in increased germination and growth. Or, an allelopathic substance that might be released by *P. distichum* reduces growth of *E. glabrescens*. Tall-growing annual grass *E. glabrescens* also might have competed with and reduced growth of shorter *P. distichum*.

The significant yield reduction was the result of weed competition, probably because of increased growth of *E. glabrescens*. No significant yield differences were found in the plots treated with butachlor or hand weeded. This indicates that *P. distichum* can be reduced with good land preparation and the annual grass population that may increase can be checked by butachlor. □

Effect of modified urea materials and N levels on transplanted rice

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Split application of urea and modified urea materials was tested in 1985 kharif.

In a field experiment laid out on a deep Vertisol (pH 7.5, 0.61% organic C, CEC 20.6 meq/ 100 g, 25.3 kg available P (Olsen)/ ha, 4.6 meq exchangeable K/ 100 g, 0.2 ppm available Zn and silty clay texture). At the last puddling, 26.4

Effect of modified urea and N level on transplanted rice. Kota, India, 1985 kharif.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)
Control (no N)	2.2	181.3
58 kg N/ha PU-BS	3.9	214.8
PU-SS	3.9	213.3
SCU-basal	4.0	237.5
USG-placement	4.1	270.0
MPCU-basal	3.9	219.0
87 kg N/ha PU-BS	4.6	241.5
PU-SS	4.5	238.3
SCU-basal	5.9	269.8
USG-placement	6.1	270.3
MPCU-basal	4.8	249.8
116 kg N/ha PU-BS	6.0	287.8
PU-SS	5.8	296.3
SCU-basal	6.0	316.8
USG-placement	6.1	329.0
MPCU-basal	5.6	268.5
CD	(0.05) 0.338.3	

^aPU-BS = prilled urea, local best split, PU-SS = prilled urea, standard split, SCU-basal = sulfur-coated urea, USG-placement = urea supergranules, and MPCU-basal = Mussooriephospho-coated urea.

Total weed weight and weight of *Echinochloa glabrescens* and *Paspalum distichum* in the unweeded plots as affected by tillage levels, and grain yield as affected by different weeding regimes.^a Nueva Ecija, Philippines.

Tillage treatment	Weed weight (g/m ²)			Grain yield (t/ha)		
	<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i>	<i>Paspalum distichum</i>	Total	No weeding	Hand weeding (21 and 35 DT)	Butachlor (0.6,3 DT)
1 plowing + 3 harrowings (within 1 mo before transplanting)	180 a	30 a	274 a	2.1 a	2.7 a	2.6 ab
1 plowing + 3 harrowings (within 2 mo before transplanting)	159 a	37 a	259 a	1.9 a	2.6 a	2.2 b
1 plowing + 3 harrowings (harrowing by hand tractor)	418 b	8 a	578 b	0.9 b	2.4 a	2.6 ab
2 plowings + 3 harrowings (animal)	53 a	60 a	141 a	2.3 a	2.0 a	2.3 b
1 plowing + 5 harrowings (animal)	127 a	62 a	214 a	2.3 a	2.6 a	3.0 a

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. DT = days after transplanting.

kg P/ha and 33.2 kg K/ha were applied. Prilled urea was applied as basal in 2-3 cm standing water.

Root zone placement (10-12 cm) of urea supergranules (USG) and basal sulfur-coated-urea (SCU) and Mussooriephos-coated urea (MPCU) at

58, 87, and 116 kg N/ha were evaluated against local best split (1/2 basal + 1/4 at maximum tillering + 1/4 at panicle initiation) and standard best split (2/3 basal + 1/3 at panicle initiation).

Maximum grain yield was with USG and SCU at all N levels (see table). USG

produced significantly higher yields than standard best split urea and MPCU at 87 and 116 kg N/ha. USG and SCU also produced significantly more panicles/m² than MPCU at 116 kg N/ha. □

Nitrogen management for increasing N efficiency in transplanted rice

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We compared the efficiency of a single application of sulfur-coated urea (SCU), urea supergranules (USG), and split application of prilled urea (PU) at

varying levels of N during 1983 kharif. The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications. Treatments were SCU, USG, and PU at 29, 58, 87, and 116 kg N/ha. Medium-duration, dwarf variety Usha was the test crop. Soil was a Vertisol (clay-loam, with 210.11 kg available N, 12.50 kg available P, 225 kg available K/ha, 0.20 mmho EC, 0.60% organic C, and pH 6.5-7.5).

Growth and yield-contributing characters were significantly superior with SCU and USG (see table). Grain

and straw yields were significantly different with different forms and levels of N.

Maximum grain yield was with SCU, followed by USG. SCU and USG were similar in N efficiency. USG produced a significantly higher straw yield than SCU and PU.

N at 116 kg/ha produced significantly high grain and straw yields. □

Grain yield and ancillary characters as influenced by sources and levels of N. Raipur, India, 1983 kharif.

Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Sources and methods of N application	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Effective tillers/m ²	Panicle weight (g)	Panicle length (cm)	Sound spikelets/panicle
0	Check	1.9	2.30	190	1.3	17	48
29	Urea, best split	2.6	2.94	206	1.7	18	62
29	SCU, broadcast and incorporated in soil	3.2	3.51	259	2.1	20	69
29	USG placed at 10-12 cm soil depth	3.2	3.77	257	1.8	19	66
	Mean	3.0	3.40	240	1.9	19	65
58	Urea, best split	3.0	3.15	243	1.9	19	67
58	SCU, broadcast and incorporated in soil	3.8	4.35	304	2.2	21	76
58	USG placed at 10-12 cm soil depth	3.7	4.97	303	2.1	20	70
	Mean	3.5	4.16	283	2.1	20	71
87	Urea, best split	3.3	3.50	277	1.9	19	68
87	SCU, broadcast and incorporated in soil	4.2	5.30	344	2.3	21	79
87	USG placed at 10-12 cm soil depth	4.1	5.84	340	2.2	21	76
	Mean	3.9	4.88	320	2.2	20	75
116	Urea, best split	3.7	4.32	335	2.1	20	72
116	SCU broadcast and incorporated in soil	4.5	6.24	409	2.5	22	82
116	USG placed at 10-12 cm soil depth	4.3	6.97	405	2.4	22	80
	Mean	4.2	5.84	383	2.3	21	78
	CD (0.05) for forms	0.2	0.40	9	0.1	0.4	5.7
	for levels	0.2	0.46	10	0.2	0.5	6.6

Nitrogen sources for flooded rice

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We evaluated prilled urea (PU), neem cake coated-urea (NCU), lac-coated urea (LCU), didin-coated urea (DCU), and urea supergranule (USG) at 40, 80, and 120 kg N/ha for transplanted rice in the 1983 and 1984 wet seasons. Experimental field soil was a fine, silty, mixed, hyperthermic, Typic Hapludoll with pH

Effect of N source and N level on yield. Pantnagar, India, 1983 and 1984 wet seasons.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	1983	1984	Mean
<i>N sources</i>			
PU	3.67	3.71	3.69
NCU	4.36	4.57	4.46
LCU	3.79	4.14	3.96
DCU	3.71	4.11	3.91
USG	4.70	4.73	4.72
SE	0.06	0.06	—
CD (0.05)	0.16	0.16	—
<i>N levels (kg/ha)</i>			
0	2.25	2.42	2.33
40	3.36	3.55	3.45
80	4.11	4.36	4.24
120	4.66	4.91	4.78
SE	0.04	0.04	—
CD (0.05)	0.12	0.12	—